

A CASE STUDY: AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF AMLAPITTA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO HYPERACIDITY

Dr. Khushbu Gondaliya^{1*}, Dr. Vaibhavi Patel², Dr. Hemang Raghavani³, Dr. Archit Adhvaryu⁴

*^{1,2,4}PG Scholar, Panchkarma Department, Government Akhandanand Ayurveda College and Hospital, Ahmedabad.

³M.D. (Ayu), PhD, Assistant Professor Panchkarma Department, Government, Akhandanand Ayurveda College and Hospital, Bhadra, Ahmedabad.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Khushbu Gondaliya

PG Scholar, Panchkarma Department,
Government Akhandanand Ayurveda
College and Hospital, Ahmedabad.

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ABSTRACT

In *Ayurveda Amlapitta* is one of the commonest *Annavaha Srotodushti Vyadhi* in which *Pitta* get *Vidhagdham* or *Amlapaka*. Causes of *Amlapitta* especially compromise *Ahara janya hetu*, such as excessive intake of *Abhishyandi* and *Pishtanna*, acidic, hot substances, alcohol, *Adhyashan*, *Viruddhshan*, *Vidahiannapana*, and intake of food in *Ajirna* condition in modern science *Amlapitta* can be correlated with hyperacidity in which excess acid production in the stomach.

Aim and Objectives: The prime aim of this paper is to study the efficacy of *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa* in *Ayurveda* in the management of *Amlapitta*. **Material and Method:** It is a single case study of 52 years-old female who had complaints *Urahaha*, *Uraha shoola*, *Sarvanga Sharira Daha*, *Amla Katu Udgat Pravrutti*, *Shirahshoola*, *Klama* and sometime *Mutradaha* since 6 years. **Observations and Results:** All clinical features in this patient had reduced significantly by

using *Shodhana (virechana)* and *Shaman Aushadhi* recommended by ancient Acharyas in the management of *Amlapitta*.

KEYWORDS: *Amlapitta*, *Virechana*, hyperacidity.

INTRODUCTION

According to Ayurvedic classics, *Agni* is responsible for *Ayu* (age), *Varna* (colour), *Bala* (power), *S washya* (health), *Utsaha* (excitement), *Upachaya* (digestion), *Prabha*, *Oja* and *Teja* and *Agni* takes a pivot role in the etiopathogenesis of all human ailments.^[1] According to *Acharya Charaka*, indulging in *Ajirna*, *Atibhojana* (over eating), *Vishama Bhojana* (irregular diet), *Asatmya* (incompatible diet) and *Sandushta Bhojana* produces *Shuktata* due to *Agni Dushti* (impairment of *Agni*) followed by *Ama* and *Amavisha* which further develops *Ajirna* (indigestion) by vitiating *Dosha*.^[2] All the diseases are caused by 'Mandagni' as *Acharya Vagbhata* says 'Roga Sarveapi Mandeagni'^[3] Continuous indulgence in improper diet and erratic lifestyle basically aggravates *Pitta Dosha* which leads the disease into acute condition of *Vidagdhajirna* (indigestion)^[4] which due to ignorance inturn converts into *Amlapitta*. The disease *Amlapitta* is one among the *Annavaha Srotodushti Vikara* The word *Amlapitta* comprises of two words – *Amla* and *Pitta*, here *Pitta* is the *Dosha* involved and *Amla* is the *Rasa* of the *Pitta*. This is a condition where the natural *Katu Rasa* of *Pitta* is replaced by *Amlata* due to *Vidagdhavasta*. In *Amlapitta* the quantity of *Pachaka Pitta* is increased causing *Shuktata* to *Annarasa* residing in *Amashaya* forming *Ama* and causing *Amlapitta*.^[5] The process of digestion being impaired due to inhibitory action imposed by the nervous system and vasovagal reflex accelerating the secretions is leading to the increased acidic state of the food and stasis of the food due to the inhibition of the motoractivity of the stomach^[6] producing the Lakshana of *Amlapitta*.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The prime aim of this paper is to study the efficacy of *shodhana* and *shamana chikitsa* in *ayurveda* in the management of *amlapitta*.

CASE REPORT

A 52 year old female patient-with complaint of

- *urah daha*
- *shirahshoola*
- *urah shoola*
- *sarvanga sharira daha*
- *amla katu udgar pravrutti*
- *klama*
- and sometime *mutradaha* since 6 years.

History of Present illness

Patient had Symptoms began approximately 20 years ago she used to do *vegavidharana, katu amla rasa sevana, akalabhojana, chinta*. Patient describes a burning sensation in upper abdomen, particularly after 1 hour of meals. The sensation often worsens when bend down or after consuming spicy or acidic foods. Occasional regurgitation of acidic fluid. Temporary relief from antacids and over-the-counter acid reducers. symptoms are initially mild but have progressively worsened. Then after since 6 years she had worst symptoms like *sarvanga daha, urah shula, mutra daha, katu amla udgar pravriti, klama, shirahshula*.

ON EXAMINATION

B.P.-110/70mmhg P.R.-74/min

R.R.-18/min Weight-55 kg

Table 1: Personal History.

Personal history	
Diet	Non-vegetarian
Appetite	less
Bowel	1 time/day
Sleep	Proper
Micturation	5-6 time/day sometime burning micturation

Table 2: Asta Vidha Pariksha.

Asta Vidha Pariksha	
Nadi	Vata-pitta
Mootra	Samyak
Mala	Samyak
Jihwa	Nirama
Shabda	Samyak
Sparsha	Anushnashita
Drik	Samyak
Aakruti	Krusha

Clinical findings

Table 3: Subjective Findings.

No.	Symptoms of Amlapitta	
1.	<i>Katu amla udgar pravriti</i> (pungent and sour eruction)	Since 6 years
2.	<i>Shirah shula</i> (headache)	
3.	<i>Klama</i> (weakness)	
4.	<i>Uraha daha</i> (burning sensation at chest)	
5.	<i>Urah shula</i> (epigastric pain)	
6.	<i>Sarvanga daha</i> (burning at body)	
7.	<i>Mutradaha</i> (burning micturation)	

Samprapti

The *Pitta Prakopakara Ahara Vihara* increases the *Drava Guna* of the *Pitta* leading to *Agnimandya*. *Ahara Rasa* formation does not take place properly and attains *Vidagdaavasta*. This *Vidagda Ahara* does not undergo *Paka* leading to the formation of *Ama*, this stays in *Amashaya* for long time and produces *Shuktata*. This *Avasta* changes the *Prakruta Katu Rasa* of *Pitta* to *Amla* or *Tikta Rasa*. This manifests the *Lakshanas* like *Amlodgara/ Tiktodgara, Hrit Kanta Daha, Aruchi*^[7] etc., other *Lakshanas*.

Table 4: Samprapti Ghataka.

<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Pachaka Pitta, Samana Vata, Kledaka Kapha</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Rasa</i>
<i>Agni</i>	<i>Jatharagni</i>
<i>Udbhava Sthana</i>	<i>Amashaya</i>
<i>Sanchara Sthana</i>	<i>Rasa</i>
<i>Adhishtana</i>	<i>Amashaya</i>
<i>Vyakta Sthana</i>	<i>Mukha, Kantha, Uraha</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Rasavaha, Annavaha</i>
<i>Srotodushti Prakara</i>	<i>Sanga, Vimargagamana</i>
<i>Rogamarga</i>	<i>Abhyantara</i>
<i>Sadhya sadhyata</i>	<i>Navottita- Sadhya Purana –Yapya</i>

Treatment

Patient was advised to stop all of his allopathic medicines and below treatment was started. *Shodhan Karma* by *Virechankarma* followed by *Shamana Chikitsa*, in this procedure patient is subjected to a time limited controlled purgation. Before this procedure, internal medicine is given for 3-5 days for proper digestion. After that the main procedure is done by internal oleation for 3-7 days followed by external oleation and sudation. During this period patient

was instructed to follow special diet regimen (*Drava, Anabhisvandi, Ushna, Naatisnigdha Bhojana and Ushna Jala*) for 3-7 days.^[9]

Virechana Karma

Table 5: Virechana Karma.

Date	Karma	Medicine	Dose		Days
5/4/2024 To 6/4/2024	<i>Deepana-pachana</i>	<i>Sanjivani vati</i>	1 tab(500 mg each) twice a day after meal		3 days
07/04/2024 To 10/04/2024	<i>Snehapan</i>	<i>Go-ghrit with Ushnodak</i>	VardhmanaMatra		4 days
			Time	Dose	
			7:00 am	30 ml	
			7:00 am	50 ml	
			7:30 am	70 ml	
			7:00 am	90 ml	
11/4/2024 To 13/4/2024	<i>Sarvanga abhyanga-swedana</i>	<i>Nirgunditaila</i>	Qs		3 days
13/4/2024	<i>Virechana karma</i>	<i>Triphala kwath : 100 ml Draksha swarasa : 50 ml At wit10:45 am Ushnodak,</i>			1 days
13/4/2024 To 17/4/2024	<i>Samsarjankarma (As madhyamashuddhi)</i>	<i>Yusha, mudga, odana, samanyabhojana</i>	Morning	Evening	5 days
			-	<i>Peya</i>	
			<i>Peya</i>	<i>Vilepi</i>	
			<i>Vilepi</i>	<i>Akruta yusha</i>	
			<i>AKruta yusha</i>	<i>Kruta yusha</i>	
<i>Kruta yusha</i>	Normal diet				

Table 6: Evaluation at the End of Virechana Karma.

<i>Antikishuddhi</i>	<i>Vaigikishuddhi</i>	<i>Laingikishuddhi</i>
<i>Kaphanta Virechana</i>	Vega – 12 Upvega -4	<i>Udaralaghavata, indriya prasnnta, kramatvitta-pitta-anila</i>

Table 7: Shamana Chikitsa.

<i>Aushdha yoga</i>	Dose	Days
<i>Sutashekhara rasa</i>	2 tab(500 mg each)	Twice a day
<i>Samshamani vati</i>	2 tab(500 mg each)	Thrice a day

OBSERVATION

There was found significant relief in symptoms of *Amlapitta*. After *SamsarajanaKarma*, *Shamana Aushada* was given for 15days. At 15th day 1st follow up was done and 2nd follow up was done at 30th day.

Table 8: Observation.

Symptoms	Before treatment (2/4/2024)	After Snehapana (10/4/2024)	After Virechana karma (17/4/2024)	After Shamana Chikitsa (15/5/2024)
<i>Katu amla udgar pravriti</i> (pungent & sour eructation)	+++	++	+	+
<i>Shirahshula</i> (headache)	+++	+++	+	+
<i>Urah daha</i> (burning sensation in chest)	+++	+++	++	+
<i>Klama</i> (weakness)	+++	+++	+	+
<i>Urah shula</i> (epigastric pain)	++	++	+	+
<i>Sarvanga daha</i> (all body burning)	+	++	+	-
<i>Mutrada</i> (burning micturation)	+	++	+	-

DISCUSSION

Patient came to us for the treatment of hyperacidity which was diagnosed with Amlapitta as per the Ayurveda classics as she was suffering from *Katu Amla Udgar Pravriti*, *Urah daha*, *Shirahshula*, *Klama*, *Urah shula*, *Sarvanga daha*, *Mutra daha*. Amlapitta is caused due to increase in *Drava* and *Amla Guna* of *Pitta*. In Amlapitta vitiation of *Annavaha srotas* occurs. *Virechana* is clearly indicated in *Annavaha srotas vyadhi*. Amlapitta is a pitta vitiated disease and *Virechana* is the best treatment for Pitta vitiated disorders.

Probable mode of Action of Karma and Drugs^[1] *Virechana karma*:

Virechana karma is the one of the major Purification method of *Panchakarma*. *Virechana* drugs contain *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, *Sukshma*, *Vyavayi* and *Vikasi Gunas*. These *Gunas* play important role in the process of *Vishyandana* of *Doshas* responsible for disease. They liquefy the *Doshas* and remove the *Doshas* out from the body. *Virechana* is the first line of treatment of *Pitta Dosh*. So *Virechana* is chosen for present treatment to correct the vitiated *dosha* in pathogenesis of *Amlapitta*.

Deepana Pachana done with *Sanjivani vati* which is mainly of *Deepana Pachana* action which improves *Jatharagni* by relieving *Ajirna*.

Snehapana done with *Go-Ghrita* which cause *Utklesh* and accumulate *Doshas* in a *Koshta*. *Virechana* drugs: *Triphala kwath* and *Draksha Swarasa* are *Virechanopaga* according to

their properties. The dominance of *Madhura rasa*, *Madhura vipaka* & *Sheeta virya* with *Prithvi* and *Jala Mahabhutadhikya* can be observed. It shows that these medicines have the natural tendency towards the downward direction. They might be helping to hold the body strength with their *Sheeta Veerya* against strong penetrating and hot properties of Virechaka drugs. The formulation *Draksha Swarasa* is used, which needs good digestive power for the action as it is considered as guru amongst all the 5 Kalpanas. The use of this specific formulation also indicate the dominance of *Pruthvi* and *Aapa Mahabhutas*.

Shamana therapy, *Kapha-Pittahara Chikitsa* is the principle of treatment for *Amlapitta*.^[2] Sutashekhar Ras: As this disease vitiated Dravya roop of Pitta is primary responsible factor. Sutshekhar Rasa have ingrediants which are mainly *Agnivardhak* and *Amapachak* properties.

Thus balances the pH of stomach and normalizes the acid base balance in gut. This drug plays very important role due to the property of its ingredient and is highly effective in the management of *Amlapitta*.^[3] *Samshamni Vati*: it acts as *Rasa Dhatvagni Vardhaka* and *Amapachaka*.

CONCLUSION

Amlapitta a disease of *Annavaha Srotas* caused due to *Ama* and *Pitta*. In this condition *Pitta* gets *Vidagdha* and becomes *Amla*. Panchakarma removes the vitiated *Dosha* and balances the morbid humour of body. patient got significant relief in her symptoms so it can be concluded that complete *Shodhanachikitsa* along with *Shamanachikitsa* can be effective in the management of *amlapitta*.

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